

feeding sites. Plants were stunted, and severely infested plants died. Sweep net (0.4 m diam, 0.5 m long) samples from highly infested fields in Raipur, Choto Jalenga, Duarbond, and Hailakandi had 800-1,400 hoppers/sweep.

Large WBPH populations were

accompanied by high rainfall in early Apr, followed by a prolonged dry period with high temperature and humidity in May. Heavy rainfall in early Jun reduced populations.

Seedlings treated with granular carbofuran 3 G or phorate 10 G at 1 g

ai/ha were free from WBPH. Spraying infested nursery seedlings with chlorpyrifos 20 EC, fenitrothion 50 EC, and phosphamidon 100 EC at 0.5 kg ai/ha also effectively controlled the pest. *J*

Effect of heavy rains on rice thrips

A. T. Barrion and J.A. Litsinger, IRRI

A slash-and-burn upland rice site in Siniloan, Laguna, Philippines, has regular high rainfall in Aug and Sep. An unusually dry spell in Aug 1985 affected the vegetative plants. Thrips settled on rice and the lack of rainfall favored their rapid multiplication in less than 2 wk. Thrips and water stress caused the rice leaves to roll and be partially dried.

Two thrips — *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) and *Haplothrips ganglbaueri* Schmut — were isolated from the damaged leaves. *S. biformis* was found only in rice. *H. ganglbaueri*, in contrast, was common in cogon grass but rare in rice. The larvae and adults of both species fed inside the rolled leaves, causing stippling damage to the leaf tissue.

In anticipation of a heavy rain, 16 thrips-infested hills of rice and the same number for cogon were covered with 10 × 64-cm cylindrical mylar cages provided with side vents. Thrips populations were counted before and after the rain on uncovered plants (n = 25 rolled leaves/sampling date) and covered plants (n = 4 hills/sampling date). During the drought period, initial *H. ganglbaueri* population was high (300 individuals per 4 hills). This was subsequently reduced to 100 after the first heavy rain on 3-4 Sep and a 2-wk continuous downpour on 8-24 Sep. *S. biformis* population likewise declined from 600 to 400 under the same weather conditions. In contrast, there was a population buildup inside the cages for both species — *S. biformis* increased from 500 to 2000 individuals and *H. ganglbaueri* swelled from 90 to 500 (see figure). Heavy rainfall, therefore, is a natural mortality factor against thrips. *J*

Effect of rainfall on grass thrips (rice: ●-●; cogon; ■-■) in Siniloan, Laguna, Philippines, 24 Aug-25 Sep 1985.

Flea beetle *Chaetocnema basalis* (Baly) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), a pest of slash-and-burn upland rice in the Philippines

A. T. Barrion and J.A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

Chaetocnema spp. are common upland rice pests extending 40° N and S of the

equator in Africa, Latin America, and Asia. *C. pulla* Chapuis transmits rice yellow mottle virus in Kenya. *C. concinnipennis* Baly in India and *C. denticulata* Stephens in Latin America cause foliage damage similar to that caused by rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Olivier), but vector no disease. In the Philippines, *C. (Tlanoma)*

Chaetocnema basalis (Baly)

1. Claveria - Pamplona, Cagayan
2. Bangui, Ilocos Norte
3. Echague, Isabela
4. Masinloc, Zambales
5. Tanauan, Batangas
6. Alfonso - Indang, Cavite
7. Siniloan, Laguna
8. Real, Quezon
9. Imperial - San Juan, Camarines Norte
10. Labo, Camarines Sur
11. Isarog, Camarines Sur
12. Matnog, Sorsogon
13. Isabel, Leyte
14. Astorgas, Capiz
15. San Miguel, Iloilo
16. Del Monte, Agusan del Sur
17. Pangantukan, Bukidnon
18. Kidapawan, North Cotabato
19. Wau, Lanao del Sur
20. Pasonanca, Zamboanga del Sur
21. Aborlan - Narra, Palawan
22. Brookes Pt., Palawan
23. Puerto Princesa City, Palawan
24. Roxas, Palawan

Distribution of *Chaetocnema basalis* (inset, scale = 1 mm) in the Philippines.

basalis is widespread (see figure) in the highlands and feeds on the seedlings of nine grasses — *Brachiaria distachya* (L.) Stapf., *Chrysopogon aciculatus* (Retz.) Trin., *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Beauv., *Digitaria ciliaris* (Retz.) Koel., *Ischaemum rugosum* Salisb., *Paspalum conjugatum* Berg., *Pennisetum*

polystachyon (L.) Schult., *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench., and *Zea mays* (L.). Host records on rice were determined by keeping adults on potted seedlings and on weeds.

C. basalis removes leaf tissue parallel to the leaf veins 1-80 d after emergence in rice planted in slash-and-burn cleared

secondary rain forest. Rice seedlings wither and die in 3-5 d. Infestation occurs only in fields less than 1000 m².

Other *Chaetocnema* species in the Philippines that feed on solanaceous and cruciferous plants differ from *C. basalis*. Adult *C. basalis* are small-bodied (male, 1.5-2.08 mm; female, 2-2.30 mm) and

glossy black, with yellow basal antennal segments, yellow-brown apices of femora, tibiae, and tarsi (see figure). The pronota are smoothly punctated and

each elytron has 10 longitudinal rows of minute pits. The tibiae of the third pair of legs possess a small apophysis along

the mid-dorsum, dorsolateral combs of hairs near the apical half, and a tooth at the apices. ♂

Granulosis of the rice brown semilooper *Mocis frugalis*

D. J. Im, Entomology Department, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Suweon, Korea; and R.M. Aguda and B.M. Shepard, Entomology Department, IRRI

Rice brown semilooper *M. frugalis* (Fab.) (Lep: Noctuidae) is one of a complex of tropical lepidopterous rice pests. It occurs in flooded rice, but is more abundant in upland rice.

M. frugalis populations seldom occur in damaging levels because they are inhibited by natural parasites, predators, and diseases.

We collected last-instar *M. frugalis* larvae that were infected with a virus disease from a lowland field near Roxas, Palawan, Philippines. Diseased larvae were lemon yellow with swollen abdominal segments (Fig. 1). At later disease stages, the larvae turned dark and milky-white fluid oozed through the integument. Examination of the fluid with a phase contrast microscope showed refractive granules with Brownian movement.

Diseased larvae were macerated in distilled water with a glass homogenizer for further identification and purification. The suspension was filtered through cotton wool and centrifuged for 30 min to remove the bacteria. The precipitate was washed three times with distilled water to obtain a crude extract.

1. Larva of *Mocis frugalis* (Fab.) infected with granulosis virus.

2. Electron micrograph of capsules of *Mocis frugalis* stained with 2% phosphotungstic acid (X 27,600). a = an aberrant, sickleform capsule.

3. Virion released from the capsule after 2 h treatment with 0.05 M NaCO₃ + 0.17 M NaCl at room temperature. (X 22,380). c = empty capsule, rv = released virion, v = virion in the capsule.

The extract was layered on a 20–70% (V/V) glycerol gradient, then centrifuged at 10,000 rev/min for 15 min in a Beckman SW 27 rotor. The virus was collected at the 35–40% glycerol band. These bands were centrifuged at 12,000 rev/min for 20 min using a Beckman Mod. L5-65 and the resulting pellet was resuspended in a small amount of water.

The virus suspension was layered on 30–65% (W/W) linear sucrose density

gradient then centrifuged at 25,000 rev/min for 90 min. The band was collected at 55% sucrose band and centrifuged again at 20,000 rev/min for 30 min. The pellet was collected, diluted with water, and the process was repeated.

After centrifugation, the purified virus capsules were resuspended in water and centrifuged at 12,000 rev/min for 20 min to form a precipitate. A small amount of the virus capsule suspension was stained in a grid for 1 min with 2% phosphotungstic acid (PTA) for electron microscope examination.

The capsules were ellipsoidal, but an aberrant sickle-form also was observed (Fig. 2). Capsules were 433 nm long and 243 nm wide. Each capsule contained a single virion (nucleocapsid). A single rod-shaped virion typical of granulosis was embedded in a capsule (Fig. 3). They averaged 301 nm long and 83 nm wide. The virions were negatively stained with 2% PTA.

Virions in the capsules were obtained after treatment on the slide with equal volume of 0.05 M NaCO₃ + 0.17 M NaCl at room temperature. The protein capsule dissolved after 2 h of gentle stirring, but the virions were released after more than 3 h.

The disease was identified as granulosis. This is the first report of it attacking *M. frugalis*. ♂

Effect of neem product foliar sprays on rice pests

H. Saroja, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Tirur 602025, India

We studied the effect of foliar spraying of three neem products on the incidence of rice pests in two field experiments at PES in Tirur. The 1984–85 trials comprised five treatments replicated four times and laid out in a simple